

Responsible Research and Innovation

augMENTOR Informal Monitoring Report

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Document information

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1. Introduction

The call for the second round of the Responsible Research and Innovation (RRI) survey was announced after the project meeting in Kaunas, in June 2024. As in the previous year, all project members received an email with the request to fill in the RRI survey and it was not mandatory to fill in the questionnaire(s). As this year's RRI survey was a re-run of the last survey, we included the same dimensions and questions that were discussed in Chapter 3 of Deliverable D2.1 [1]. All dimensions along with the respective statements can be found in Appendix 1. In the following section, we present the results of this year's survey, in comparison to the 2023 survey. One should note that we do not know whether the same people took part in both surveys, which is why the differences and similarities in the survey results' should be viewed with caution. All anonymized data for 2023 and 2024 are publicly available via Zenodo [2], [3]. This work is based upon [4] and [5].

2. Qualitative survey on RRI

2.1. Demographics

This year, nine (9) people (4 women, 5 men) from seven (7) different institutions participated in the survey. One response was disregarded, as the participant only answered the first three questions. The most frequently mentioned roles in the project were Work Package (WP) Leader (n=3) and team member (n=3).

2.2. Qualitative Survey Results

Dimension of Gender Equality. The first statement (GE1) of the dimension 'Gender Equality' dealt with the equal participation of women and men in research and project management. Most participants (n=7) agreed that the participation of women and men in the project was balanced in their organization (Figure 1). GE2 -- having organizational arrangements to support women's advancement -- shows a similar picture with most respondents agreeing (n=6). The last statement for Gender Equality (GE3) examined the active integration of gender dimensions. Again, most of the participants (n=6) agreed with this statement. Based on the current participants, their perceptions of GE1 are better than last round's perceptions. Table 1 shows a comparison of the responses from the 2023 and 2024 survey for the dimension Gender Equality.

Statements on Gender Equality

Figure 1: RRI statement on the dimension of Gender Equality

Table 1: Percentage distribution of votes for the dimension of Gender Equality in 2023 an 2024.

Year	Statement	disagree	Neither disagree nor agree	agree	Don't know
2023	GE1	9 (43%)	0	12 (57%)	n=0
	GE2	0	2 (9%)	18 (82%)	n=2 (9%)
	GE3	0	1 (5%)	21 (95%)	n=0
2024	GE1	1 (11.11%)	1 (11.11%)	7 (77.78%)	0
	GE2	1 (11.11%)	1 (11.11%)	6 (66.67%)	1 (11.11%)
	GE3	1 (11.11%)	1 (11.11%)	6 (66.67%)	1 (11.11%)

Engagement. The first statement (E1) refers to whether tools and mechanisms for stakeholder dialogues are used. Most participants (n=8) agreed with that statement (Figure 2). For the second statement (E2), we see a similar picture, where most respondents (n=7) agreed to using a systematic approach for including various stakeholders' viewpoints. In the third statement (E3), participants were asked to consent

to including end users in the design and development process. Most respondents agreed with this statement. Again, most respondents (n=6) agreed. Statement E4 is concerned with the involvement of potential non-users and indirect stakeholders in the design and development process. Two respondents stated that they neither disagree nor agree while two other respondents said they 'don't know'. Five respondents agreed with this statement. For the next statement (E5), participants assessed the involvement of society groups / non-governmental organizations (NGOs) in the design and development phase. There was no consensus on this statement (Figure 2). Two people either disagreed or 'didn't know', 3 people said they would 'neither disagree nor agree' and only 2 people agreed. Statement E6 focused on the involvement of policymakers in the design and development process. Again, participants show different points of view, but at least four (4) participants agree. For the last statement (E7), which dealt with science communication and education activities to educate citizens and generate awareness of the innovations the organizations are working on, we see slightly more agreement (n=5).

Statements on Engagement

Figure 2. RRI statement on the dimension of Engagement

Participants perceived E1, E2 and E3 slightly better than last round's participants, whereas the agreement with statements E3, E5 and E6 has decreased for this year's participants. Table 2 shows a comparison of the votes from the 2023 and 2024 survey for the dimension Engagement.

Table 2: Distribution of votes for the dimension of Engagement in 2023 an 2024.

Year	Statement	disagree	Neither disagree nor agree	agree	Don't know
2023	E1	1 (5%)	4 (18%)	16 (73%)	1 (5%)
	E2	1 (5%)	3 (14%)	16 (73%)	2 (9%)
	E3	1 (5%)	1 (5%)	20 (91%)	0
	E4	0	8 (36%)	11 (50%)	3 (14%)
	E5	0	4 (18%)	15 (68%)	3 (14%)
	E6	1 (5%)	5 (23%)	13 (59%)	3 (14%)
	E7	4 (18%)	6 (27%)	12 (55%)	0
2024	E1	0	0	8 (89%)	1 (11%)
	E2	0	1 (11%)	7 (78%)	1 (11%)
	E3	0	1 (13%)	6 (75%)	1 (13%)
	E4	0	2 (22%)	5 (56%)	2 (22%)
	E5	2 (22%)	3 (33%)	2 (22%)	2 (22%)
	E6	1 (11%)	2 (22%)	4 (44%)	2 (22%)
	E7	1 (11%)	1 (11%)	5 (56%)	2 (22%)

Legislative Landscape. The first statement (LL1) examined whether current regulation and legislative landscapes do not pose problems for the project. The second statement (LL2) refers to the existence of a code of conduct/ ethical review board. For both statements, the majority of participants agreed (n=7 for LL1, n=6 for LL2), whereas two participants each chose they 'don't know'. For the second statement, one person (1) neither disagreed nor agreed (Figure 3).

Statements on Legislative Landscape

Figure 3: RRI statement on the dimension of Legislative Landscape

This round's respondents' perception with the second statement (LL2) decreased slightly. Table 3 shows a comparison of the votes from the 2023 and 2024 survey for the dimension Legislative Landscape.

Table 3: Distribution of votes for the dimension of Legislative Landscape in 2023 an 2024.

Year	Statement	disagree	Neither disagree nor agree	agree	Don't know
2023	LL1	1 (5%)	4 (18%)	17 (77%)	0
	LL2	0	2 (9%)	18 (82%)	2 (9%)
2024	LL1	0	0	7 (78%)	2 (22%)
	LL2	0	1 (11%)	6 (67%)	2 (22%)

Assessment. The first statement (A1) refers to continuously monitoring ethical aspects. Apart from one (1) participant, all other participants (n=8) agreed with this statement (Figure 4). The second statement (A2) deals with the continuous consultation of other researchers and research projects to signal new and future trends. Again, most of the participants agreed with the statement (n=7). Statement A3 asked participants to rate their level of agreement on the regular organization of group deliberation activities for the project. For this statement, five (5) people agreed, whereas one person (1) disagreed, two (2) did neither disagree nor agree and one (1) chose don't know. Statement four

(A4) focused on the analysis or monitoring of the impact of the products/services of the project. Two (2) participants disagreed, one (1) chose to neither disagree nor agree and 2 chose don't know. Whereas only four (4) people agreed.

The current participants perceive A2, A3 and A4 worse than last round's participants. Table 4 shows a comparison of the votes from the 2023 and 2024 survey for the dimension Assessment.

Statements on Assessment

Figure 4: RRI statement on the dimension of Assessment

Table 4: Distribution of votes for the dimension of Assessment in 2023 an 2024.

Year	Statement	disagree	Neither disagree nor agree	agree	Don't know
2023	A1	0	1 (5%)	21 (95%)	0
	A2	0	1 (5%)	21 (95%)	0
	A3	1 (5%)	7 (32%)	14 (64%)	0
	A4	3 (14%)	5 (23%)	14 (64%)	0
2024	A1	0	0	8 (89%)	1 (11%)
	A2	0	1 (11%)	7 (78%)	1 (11%)
	A3	1 (11%)	2 (22%)	5 (56%)	1 (11%)
	A4	2 (22%)	1 (11%)	4 (44%)	2 (22%)

Public and Ethical Issues. For the first statement (PEI1) in the dimension 'Public and Ethical Issues' participants were asked to rate their level of agreement about the documentation of best practices about ethical acceptability for the project during the development. Two people (2) chose to neither disagree nor agree, and two (2) chose they 'don't know'; the remaining four (4) people agreed (Figure 5). The second statement (PEI2) claimed that there has been little public resistance against the use of the outcome of the project. Again, four (4) people agreed, while every other option was selected once.

The perception of the current participants of PE1 is worse than that of last round's participants, whereas the perception of PEI2 is slightly better. Table 5 shows a comparison of the votes from the 2023 and 2024 survey for the dimension Public and Ethical Issues.

Statements on Public and Ethical Issues

Figure 5: RRI statement on the dimension of Public and Ethical Issues

Table 5: Distribution of votes for the dimension of Public and Ethical Issues in 2023 and 2024.

Year	Statement	disagree	Neither disagree nor agree	agree	Don't know
2023	PEI1	0	1 (5%)	20 (91%)	1 (5%)
	PEI2	3 (14%)	5 (23%)	12 (55%)	2 (9%)
2024	PEI1	0	2 (25%)	4 (50%)	2 (25%)
	PEI2	1 (14%)	1 (14%)	4 (57%)	1 (14%)

Responsiveness and Adaptive Change. The first statement (RAC1) refers to the active and continuous inclusion of values and normative principles in research and technological design. As depicted in Figure 6, except for one (1) participant who chose to neither disagree nor agree, all participants (n=7) agreed to this statement. For the second statement (RAC2), participants were asked to express their agreement about the application of risk identification and risk management strategies. One person (1) chose they 'don't know' and all other respondents agreed (n=6). The third statement (RAC3) looked upon adopting a learning approach to adapt the research program according to the viewpoints and ideas of stakeholders. While six (6) people agreed to this statement,

two (2) said they ‘don’t know’. The participants in this round slightly perceive that RAC1, RAC2 and RAC3 are slightly worse than the participants in the last round. Table 6 shows a comparison of the votes from the 2023 and 2024 survey for the dimension Responsiveness and Adaptive Change.

Statements on Responsiveness and Adaptive Change

Figure 6: RRI statement on the dimension of Responsiveness and Adaptive Change

Table 6: Distribution of votes for the dimension of Responsiveness and Adaptive Change in 2023 an 2024.

Year	Statement	disagree	Neither disagree nor agree	agree	Don't know
2023	RAC1	0	1 (5%)	21 (95%)	0
	RAC2	0	0	22 (100%)	0
	RAC3	0	3 (14%)	18 (82%)	1 (5%)
2024	RAC1	0	1 (13%)	7 (88%)	0
	RAC2	0	0	6 (86%)	1 (14%)
	RAC3	0	0	6 (75%)	2 (25%)

Intellectual Property and Confidentiality. Respondents were asked to rate their agreement about Intellectual Property in the form of patent application or acquiring licenses not playing a large role for the organization (IPC1). As can be seen from Figure 7, the level of agreement is not very balanced. Two (2) people disagreed, whereas three (3) agreed and three (3) others chose they 'don't know'. Statement IPC2 referred to the confidentiality of methods and results not being an issue within the research and development for the project. Again, the respondents are not very consistent in their votes. Three (3) respondents disagreed, while three (3) others chose to neither disagree nor agree and only two (2) respondents agreed. The last statement dealt with personal data and privacy issues not playing a major role in the project (IPC3). Figure 7 shows that all participants (n=8) were consistent and disagreed with this statement.

The levels of agreement for this year's participants for IPC1 and IPC2 are not very balanced, similar to the previous round. Table 7 shows a comparison of the votes from the 2023 and 2024 survey for the dimension Intellectual Property and Confidentiality.

Statements on Intellectual Property and Confidentiality

Figure 7: RRI statement on the dimension of Intellectual Property and Confidentiality

Table 7: Distribution of votes for the dimension of Intellectual Property and Confidentiality in 2023 and 2024.

Year	Statement	disagree	Neither disagree nor agree	agree	Don't know
2023	IPC1	6 (27%)	6 (27%)	6 (27%)	4 (18%)
	IPC2	6 (27%)	6 (27%)	9 (41%)	1 (5%)
	IPC3	13 (59%)	4 (18%)	4 (18%)	1 (5%)
2024	IPC1	2 (25%)	0	3 (38%)	3 (38%)
	IPC2	3 (38%)	3 (38%)	2 (25%)	0
	IPC3	8 (100%)	0	0	0

Social Sustainability. The first statement covered the active inclusion of societal values in the design process (SCS1). All participants (n=7) agreed with this statement (Figure 8). Subsequently, a statement about the provision of substantial and societal benefits in comparison to available alternatives (SCS2) was presented to the participants. For this statement, two (2) people chose to neither disagree nor agree and one (1) person said they 'don't know', while five (5) people expressed their agreement. The third statement mentioned the implementation of the outcomes of the project not being hindered by issues of trust (SCS3). Again, five (5) people agreed, while one (1) person disagreed and two (2) people chose they 'don't know'. The last statement (SCS4) referred to the implementation of the outcomes of the project in society not being dependent on societal support. As can be seen in Figure 8, this time most respondents chose to neither disagree nor agree (n=4), while only one (1) person agreed, one (1) person disagreed and two (2) said they 'don't know'.

Based on the participants, their perceptions of SCS1 are slightly better compared to last round's participants. For SCS2, the perception slightly decreased. Table 8 shows a comparison of the votes from the 2023 and 2024 survey for the dimension Social Sustainability.

Statements on Social Sustainability

Figure 8: RRI statement on the dimension of Social Sustainability

Table 8: Distribution of votes for the dimension of Social Sustainability in 2023 and 2024.

Year	Statement	disagree	Neither disagree nor agree	agree	Don't know
2023	SCS1	0	0	21 (95%)	1 (5%)
	SCS2	0	5 (23%)	16 (73%)	1 (5%)
	SCS3	2 (9%)	6 (27%)	14 (64%)	0
	SCS4	5 (23%)	12 (55%)	4 (18%)	1 (5%)
2024	SCS1	0	0	7 (100%)	0
	SCS2	0	2 (25%)	5 (63%)	1 (13%)
	SCS3	1 (13%)	0	5 (63%)	2 (25%)
	SCS4	1 (13%)	4 (50%)	1 (13%)	2 (25%)

Open Access. The first statement (OA1) mentions the fact that the project makes use of virtual platforms for data exchange inside the organizations. As can be seen in Figure 9, all participants (n=8) expressed their agreement. Statement OA2 refers to using virtual platforms for data exchange with stakeholders. Except for one (1) participant who disagreed, all other participants (n=7) agreed to this. Statement OA3 asked participants to rate their agreement regarding the active communication of results within the research network. As for statement OA1, all participants (n=8) agreed. For the next statement - about the usage of institutional mechanisms for promoting the results of the organization's Research and Development (R&D) activities publicly after the activities have finished (OA4) - one person (1) said they don't know whereas 7 people agreed. The last statement (OA5) looks upon the usage of institutional mechanisms for promoting the results of the organization's R&D activities to involve stakeholder groups after the activities have finished. Here, one (1) participant said they neither agreed nor disagree and one (1) chose they 'don't know' while six (6) participants agreed.

Based on current participants, their perceptions of OA1, OA2, OA3, and OA4 are better. Table 9 shows a comparison of the votes from the 2023 and 2024 survey for the dimension Open Access.

Statements on Open Access

Figure 9: RRI statement on the dimension of Open Access

Table 9: Distribution of votes for the dimension of Open Access in 2023 and 2024.

Year	Statement	disagree	Neither disagree nor agree	agree	Don't know
2023	OA1	0	3 (14%)	18 (82%)	1 (5%)
	OA2	2 (9%)	2 (9%)	14 (64%)	4 (18%)
	OA3	0	2 (9%)	20 (91%)	0
	OA4	0	1 (5%)	19 (90%)	1 (5%)
	OA5	0	3 (14%)	16 (73%)	3 (14%)
2024	OA1	0	0	8 (100%)	0
	OA2	1 (13%)	0	7 (88%)	0
	OA3	0	0%	8 (100%)	0
	OA4	0	0	7 (88%)	1 (13%)
	OA5	0	1 (13%)	6 (75%)	1 (13%)

Previous Experience with RRI. At the end of the survey, participants were asked to rate their familiarity with the concept of RRI on a scale from 1 “not familiar at all” to 5 “extremely familiar”. The results are displayed in Figure 10. The results for this year/ the second round are displayed in dark blue. Most of the participants (n=6) chose the middle of the given scale and nobody indicated to be not familiar at all (option 1) or extremely familiar (option 5). Participants could also reply to the open question how they would describe their previous experience with the concept of RRI. Here, four (4) participants mentioned that they had some experience from last year’s survey or the project input on RRI.

Compared to last year’s survey results, the variance of the answers was not so wide. Last year, we saw more respondents choosing option 1 (27% in 2023, 0% in 2024) and option 2 (23% in 2023 and 11% in 2024). This year, more respondents chose option 3 (67% in 2024 compared to 32% in 2023) and option 4 (22% in 2024 compared to 18% in 2023).

Familiarity with RRI

Figure 10: Distribution of the project partners with regards to their familiarity with RRI

3. Quantitative survey

The second survey aimed to gather quantitative information from the project coordinators regarding the management and implementation activities of the project. The results are displayed in Table 10. Comparing the results from this round with those of the previous round, it is noticeable that it was possible to give much more specific answers this year. Last year, for example, it was often mentioned that one should look for the information in the respective deliverables, whereas this time many concrete numbers were given as an answer.

Table 10: Results of the quantitative survey for the second monitoring round of RRI

Question	Participant
What is the number of training sessions / meetings per year to learn and reflect on moral values connected to innovation strategy and core business?	2
What is the number of training sessions / meetings per year aiming to reflect on integration of social and ethical values into specific R&I/R&D activities?	2
Are RRI principles formally integrated into the augMENTOR project's mission and vision (e.g., ethical code of conduct)?	yes
What is the number of R&I/R&D activities per year where moral values are actively and included into innovation strategies and technological design?	3
What is the number of R&I/R&D activities per year where internal / external stakeholders were involved from the early stages in product development?	5
What is the number of consultancy initiatives with other innovators and external advisors to discuss and identify social impacts of R&I / R&D activities?	4
What is the number of stakeholder	2

engagement initiatives organized per year by the augMENTOR project?	
What is the number of R&I / R&D activities per year where active stakeholder engagement is foreseen into R&I / R&D plans?	2
What is the number of R&I / R&D activities per year where engagement with end-users has been performed?	Not applicable
What is the percentage of men and women involved in R&I / R&D function / teams in the augMENTOR project?	46%M - 54%F
What formal communication strategies are established to ensure most relevant RRI choices are explained in key documents and / or the website?	E-mails, online discussions
What is the number of patents per year aiming to integrate non-financial values?	Not applicable
What is the number of open access publications?	10
What is the number of events or webpages or channels in social media (or similar) disseminating project results to the general public?	5
What is the number of user-centered approaches per year formally integrated into the project's innovation model (e.g. user-centered design, co-creation)?	3
What is the number of user experience tools per year carried-out to respond to (new) societal demands and developments?	Not applicable
What is the number of R&I / R&D activities per year addressing socially / ethically-oriented products / services?	2

What is the number of R&I / R&D activities per year that apply impact analysis strategies (e.g. risk management, ethical/ social impact analysis, etc.)?	1
What formal external auditing procedures are in place to monitor non-financial values of the project?	Ethics Board, EC evaluation

4. Conclusion

To compare the years 2023 and 2024, we have provided tables with the different agreement rates. For the project, it is interesting to look at these tables and yet we cannot really compare the data. This is due to the fact that considerably fewer participants took part this year ($n=9$) compared to last year ($n=22$). We did not collect information we could relate to the previous survey and therefore we do not know whether the same people took part in both surveys or whether other people took part this year. The development of whether there is more or less agreement cannot therefore be traced back to a causality. Nevertheless it is concerning that only few people took part in the second round of the survey even if we stressed the importance of the project. At the same time, however, we can also note a positive development as some people ($n=4$) responded to be familiar with the concept of RRI due to previous RRI-related activities within the project (e.g. the previous questionnaire and the discussion of the results or the RRI workshop we conducted during the second plenary meeting). For the future, we plan to have a third round of the RRI questionnaires emphasize the importance of the topic once again in the upcoming project meetings.

References

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Annex 1: RRI Survey questionnaire 1

Below, we list the dimensions and statements of the RRI survey that was shared with the whole project team, once in 2023 and once in 2024. Furthermore, we share the percentage votes from the 2023 and 2024 survey. The percentages are illustrated in two figures, which show the percentages for 2023 and 2024 respectively.

Gender Equality

GE1: Within the project, we (that is, our organization) have equal participation of women and men in both research and project management.

GE2: We (that is, our organization) have organizational arrangements to progressively eliminate barriers impeding women's advancement to top positions and factors inducing women to drop out of science.

GE3: In our organization, the integration of gender dimensions is actively integrated in research and innovation outcomes.

Percentage distribution of votes for Gender Equality 2023

Figure 11: Percentage distribution of votes for the dimension of Gender Equality - results from 2023

Percentage distribution of votes for Gender Equality 2024

Figure 12: Percentage distribution of votes for the dimension of Gender Equality - results from 2024

Engagement.

E1: We (that is, our organization) use tools and mechanisms for organizing dialogue with stakeholders on appraisal / ethical acceptability for the purpose of the augMENTOR project.

E2: We (that is, our organization) used a systematic approach (specified how, when and why) from the beginning to include various stakeholder viewpoints on a wide set of values (technical, social, ethical, legal, etc.) for the purpose of the augMENTOR project.

E3: We (that is, our organization) include input of end users in the design and development process for the purpose of the augMENTOR project.

E4: We (that is, our organization) include input of possible non-users / indirect stakeholders in the design and development process for the purpose of the augMENTOR project.

E5: We (that is, our organization) include input of civil society groups / NGOs in the design and development process for the purpose of the augMENTOR project.

E6: We (that is, our organization) include input of policy makers in the design and development process for the purpose of the augMENTOR project.

E7: We (that is, our organization) organize science communication / education activities aimed at educating citizens and generating awareness of aspects/ issues of the innovations we are working on for the purpose of the augMENTOR project.

Percentage distribution of votes for Engagement 2023

Figure 13: Percentage distribution of votes for the dimension of Engagement - results from 2023

Percentage distribution of votes for Engagement 2024

Figure 14: Percentage distribution of votes for the dimension of Engagement - results from 2024

Legislative Landscape:

LL1: Current regulation and the legislative landscape for this type of project provides no

problems to our project from the perspective of our organization.

LL2: We (that is, our organization) have an official code of conduct / ethical review board that safeguards that this project can be carried out without issues.

Percentage distribution of votes for Legislative Landscape 2023

Figure 15: Percentage distribution of votes for the dimension of Legislative Landscape - results from 2023

Percentage distribution of votes for Legislative Landscape 2024

Figure 16: Percentage distribution of votes for the dimension of Legislative Landscape - results from 2024

Assessment:

A1: We (that is, our organization) use on-going, continuous monitoring of ethical aspects in this project.

A2: We (that is, our organization) continuously consult other researchers and research projects to signal new and future technological trends for the purpose of the augMENTOR project.

A3: We (that is, our organization) regularly organize group deliberation (employee engagement, trainings, discussions, etc.) on societal/ social/ public/ policy aspects for the purpose of the augMENTOR project.

A4: We (that is, our organization) have conducted analysis on (or have monitored) the impact of the products/services of this project.

Percentage distribution of votes for Assessment 2023

Figure 17: Percentage distribution of votes for the dimension of Assessment - results from 2023

Percentage distribution of votes for Assessment 2024

Figure 18: Percentage distribution of votes for the dimension of Assessment - results from 2024

Public and Ethical Issues

PEI1: We (that is, our organization) document best practices about ethical acceptability for this project during its development.

PEI2: There has, historically, been little public resistance against the use of the outcome of this project.

Percentage distribution of votes for Public and Ethical Issues 2023

Figure 19: Percentage distribution of votes for the dimension of Public and Ethical Issues - results from 2023

Percentage distribution of votes for Public and Ethical Issues 2024

Figure 20: Percentage distribution of votes for the dimension of Public and Ethical Issues - results from 2024

Responsiveness and Adaptive Change

RAC1: We (that is, our organization) actively and continuously include values and normative principles (health, safety, security, privacy, accountability, etc.) in research, and technological design for the purpose of this project.

RAC2: We (that is, our organization) apply risk identification and risk management strategies to adjust the course of this project.

RAC3: We (that is, our organization) adopt a learning approach to adapt the research program according to the viewpoints and ideas of other stakeholders for the purpose of this project.

Percentage distribution of votes for Responsiveness and Adaptive Change 2023

Figure 21: Percentage distribution of votes for the dimension of Responsiveness and Adaptive Change - results from 2023

Percentage distribution of votes for Responsiveness and Adaptive Change 2024

Figure 22: Percentage distribution of votes for the dimension of Responsiveness and Adaptive Change - results from 2024

Intellectual Property and Confidentiality

IPC1: For this project, Intellectual Property (IP) in the form of patent applications (from our side) or acquiring licenses (from others) do not play a large role for our organization.

IPC2: Confidentiality of methods and results is not an issue within this research and development project for our organization.

IPC3: Personal data and privacy issues do not play a major role in this project, once its outcomes are used, for our organization.

Percentage distribution of votes for Intellectual Property and Confidentiality 2023

Figure 23: Percentage distribution of votes for the dimension of Intellectual Property and Confidentiality - results from 2023

Percentage distribution of votes for Intellectual Property and Confidentiality 2024

Figure 24: Percentage distribution of votes for the dimension of Intellectual Property and Confidentiality - results from 2024

Social Sustainability

SCS1: Societal values (privacy, safety, health, security, data ownership, etc.) are actively included in the design process of this project.

SCS2: This project provides substantial societal benefits, compared to available alternatives (health, safety, solidarity, equity).

SCS3: The implementation of the outcomes of this project in society are not hampered by issues of trust.

SCS4: The implementation of the outcomes of this project in society is not dependent on societal support.

Percentage distribution of votes for Social Sustainability 2023

Figure 25: Percentage distribution of votes for the dimension of Social Sustainability - results from 2023

Percentage distribution of votes for Social Sustainability 2024

Figure 26: Percentage distribution of votes for the dimension of Social Sustainability - results from 2024

Open Access

OA1: This project makes use of virtual platforms for data exchange for use inside our organization (e.g., laboratory notebooks, meeting minutes, etc.).

OA2: This project makes use of virtual platforms for data exchange (sharing) with stakeholders and our organization.

OA3: Research results are actively communicated within the research network (stakeholders) of our organization during the project.

OA4: This project uses institutional mechanisms for promoting the results of our organization's R&D activities publicly after these activities are finished.

OA5: This project uses institutional mechanisms for promoting the results of our organization's R&D activities to involve stakeholder groups after these activities are finished.

Percentage distribution of votes for Open Access 2023

Figure 27: Percentage distribution of votes for the dimension of Open Access - results from 2023

Percentage distribution of votes for Open Access 2024

Figure 28: Percentage distribution of votes for the dimension of Open Access - results from 2024